

Electrometric Investigations on the System Acid-Ortho Arsenite

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The precise nature of the reaction between acids (HCl and CH₃COOH) and alkali ortho-arsenite has been investigated by means of *pH*, E.M.F. and conductance measurements. The well-defined breaks and inflexions in titration curves provide cogent evidence for the formation of meta-arsenite, NaAsO₂, and meta arsenious acid, HAsO₂, at *pH* ranges 9.7-10.2 and 4.5-5.5 respectively; the formation of pyro-arsenite Na₄As₂O₇ is, however, not indicated. The shape of the titration curves reveals that ortho-arsenite does not exist as such but hydrolyses to form a mixture of NaOH and lower arsenites.

A survey of literature reveals that the chemistry of oxy-acids of arsenic is complicated and no finality seems to have been reached as to the constitution of arsenious acid derived from arsenic trioxide, and to their respective alkali metal derivatives. It has been reported that arsenious acid exists in solution but to a very limited degree since it decomposes with great ease into its anhydride and water¹. This anhydride is, however, slightly soluble in water and the solution has weakly acidic nature. The formula to be assigned to arsenious acid has not yet been settled. The possibility that it should be formulated as the meta-acid HAsO₂, or AsO(OH), or as a hexahydroxo-acid, H₃ [As(OH)₆] should also be considered in addition to the customary formulation as the ortho-acid H₃AsO₃². On account of this constitutional complexity with arsenious acid, the possible existence of various alkali arsenites has been reported in the literature corresponding to the different ratios of alkali oxide to arsenious oxide.³ Moreover, alkali arsenites are strongly hydrolysed and can be titrated by acids as free alkali⁴ and have a tendency of extremely easy mutual conversion to hydrated forms; as a result of which the heavy metal arsenites obtained by precipitation belong sometimes to one form and sometime to another⁵. The existence of so many alkali arsenites is, therefore, doubtful and the conclusions of the earlier reports do not provide a clear picture of the formation and composition of alkali arsenites.

Hence it was considered of interest to make a detailed study of the degradation of alkali ortho-arsenite on acidification with acids, by recent electrometric techniques, which have provided more conclusive evidences on the formation of molybdate, tungstate, and vanadate isopoly anions.⁶⁻¹⁰

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EXPERIMENTAL

Anal. R. (BDH) reagents, As_2O_3 , NaOH , HCl and CH_3COOH were used and their solutions prepared in air-free distilled water. The solution of sodium ortho-arsenite was prepared by dissolving arsenious trioxide in boiling solution of NaOH containing six moles of it per mole of As_2O_3 .

pH and E.M.F. measurements were carried out on a Cambridge (null deflection type) pH meter. A glass electrode of the range 0-14 pH , calibrated frequently by using buffers of different pH values, and an indicator electrode made of platinum foil were used in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode. Twenty five ml. of the ortho-arsenite solution was taken in the cell each time and thermostated at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The observed changes in pH and E.M.F. were plotted as a function of the volume of acid added. As the inflections in these curves were not clearly marked, differential graphs in $d\text{pH}/dV$ and dE/dV were also drawn and the end-points were judged by the pronounced maxima in $d\text{pH}/dV$ and dE/dV (figs. 2 and 4).

Fig. 1. pH titrations between acids (HCl , curve-1; CH_3COOH , curve-2) and Sodium ortho-arsenite. Curve I. ml. of $\text{M}/10$ HCl added to 25 ml. of $\text{M}/100$ Na_3AsO_3 . Curve II. ml. of $\text{M}/5$ CH_3COOH added to 25 ml. of $\text{M}/50$ Na_3AsO_3 .

Fig. 2. Plots of $d\text{pH}/dV$ against ml of acids added.

Conductance measurements were performed by means of an electronic eye type conductometer (W.T.W., Germany). Twenty five ml. of the titre was taken in cell each time and the end-points were located graphically.

Using different concentrations of the reactants, a series of glass electrode, E.M.F. and conductometric titrations were carried out. The results have been summarised in Table I and illustrated in figures (1-4).

Job's method of continuous variation, using electrical conductance measurements, was also employed for determining the stoichiometry of the arsenites formed by the interaction of acids (HCl and CH_3COOH) and ortho-arsenite. The differences in specific conductivities (sum of the conductivity of constituent solutions minus observed specific conductivity of the mixtures) were plotted against the composition of mixtures (fig. 5). From the maxima obtained in such plots, the stoichiometry of the compound formed was established.

TABLE I

Summary of the results of electrometric titrations

Molarity of solutions.		Equivalence points for the formation of								
HCl	Na_3AsO_3	NaAsO_2				HAsO_2				
		Calc.	A	B	C	Calc.	A	B	C	
Study with HCl.										
M/10	M/100	5.00	4.95	5.00	5.00	7.50	7.45	7.45	7.45	
M/20	M/250	4.00	3.90	3.85	4.00	6.00	5.90	5.95	6.00	
M/30	M/400	4.76	3.70	3.75	3.60	5.64	5.60	5.60	5.62	
Study with CH_3COOH										
M/5	M/50	5.00	5.00	5.00	—	7.50	7.40	7.50	—	
M/10	M/100	5.00	5.00	5.00	—	7.50	7.40	7.55	—	
M/20	M/250	4.00	4.10	3.85	—	6.00	5.90	6.05	—	

A, B and C represent conductometric, *pH* and E.M.F. titrations respectively.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1, curve 1 represents the changes occurring in H^+ concentration on the addition of HCl to alkali ortho-arsenite solution. It is noted that the addition of about 1.8 moles of acid per mole of ortho-arsenite does not cause any appreciable change in the *pH* of the system; in turn a buffer region between *pH* 12.2—11.5 is established showing strong affinity for the hydrogen ions in this region; subsequently the addition of HCl beyond two moles of HCl per mole of arsenite causes a rapid decrease in the *pH*, indicating an inflection at the molar ratio $\text{Na}_3\text{AsO}_3 : \text{HCl} = 1 : 2$, corresponding to the formation of alkali meta arsenite NaAsO_2 . Further addition of acid yields one more inflection indicating the consumption of three moles of HCl per mole of Na_3AsO_3 and suggesting the formation of meta-arsenious acid HAsO_2 . The *pH* of such acidified solutions became steady only after the lapse of some time indicating that the reaction proceeds by way of some unstable intermediate species. It is noted that in the case of moderately concentrated solutions, the curves are steeper and $d\text{pH}/dV$ more pronounced than for diluted reactants (fig. 2). Out of two inflections in the curves, the one corresponding to the conversion of ortho-arsenite into meta-arsenious acid is more marked.

Conductometric titrations between HCl and Na_3AsO_3 were also carried out using similar concentrations of the reagents for the sake of comparison of results. The observed

breaks indicate the formation of alkali meta-arsenite, NaAsO_2 and meta-arsenious acid HAsO_2 (fig. 3). A rapid diminution in conductance values was observed during the reaction upto the first equivalence point which corresponds to the formation of meta-arsenite NaAsO_2 which reveals that the salt must be considerably hydrolysed. This change was caused by the removal of hydroxyl ions by the direct conversion of hydrolysed alkali into the corresponding salt. This is in agreement with the glass electrode titration curves of ortho-arsenite which show high $p\text{H}$ values during the addition of two moles of acid per mole of ortho-arsenite. This leads us to infer that the ortho-arsenite hydrolyses giving hydroxyl ions and lower arsenites.

Fig. 3 Conductometric titrations between acids (HCl, curve-I, CH_3COOH , curve-2) and Sodium ortho-arsenite.

Curve-I ml of $M/10$ HCl added to 25 ml. of $M/100$ Na_3AsO_3 .

Curve-II ml of $M/5$ CH_3COOH added to 25 ml of $M/50$ Na_3AsO_3 .

Potentiometric titrations also yield two inflections (fig. 4)—one which is less prominent, corresponds to the formation of meta-arsenite and the second well-defined break confirms the formation of meta-arsenious acid.

In all these titrations an abnormal inflection occurs at the stage of the formation of meta-arsenious acid; thereafter the solution becomes acidic which is shown by a sharp increase in conductance values and pronounced maxima in $d\text{pH}/dV$ and dE/dV .

The composition of the alkali arsenites was also determined by Job's method of continuous variation. One sharp maxima (fig. 5) was obtained at the molecular ratio of ortho-arsenite: $\text{HCl} = 1 : 2$ confirming the formation of meta-arsenite. The stepwise degradation

Fig. 4 Potentiometric titrations between $M/10$ HCl and $M/100$ Na_3AsO_3 (25 ml).

of ortho-arsenite on acidification can be shown as follows :—

Where A = Cl_3^- or CH_3COO^-

* $2(\text{Na}_3\text{AsO}_3)$ is represented as $3 \text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{O}_3$ and 2NaAsO_2 as $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{As}_2\text{O}_3$.

Fig. 5 Continuous Variation Study between acids (HCl, curve-I; CH_3COOH , Curve-II) and Sodium ortho-arsenite. Curve-I M/20 HCl Vs. M/20 Na_3AsO_3 . Curve-II M/10 CH_3COOH Vs. M/10 Na_3AsO_3 .

The course of reaction between acetic acid and alkali ortho-arsenite was also studied by measuring the changes in *pH* and conductance. The breaks and inflections in the titration curves (figs. 1 and 3) provide sufficient evidence in favour of the formation of alkali meta-arsenite and meta-arsenious acid. The titration curves were found to be identical with those of HCl on almost the entire region.

The results of electrometric experiments on the acid-ortho-arsenite system suggest the formation of alkali meta-arsenite and arsenious acid at *pH* 9.7–10.2 and 4.5–5.5 respectively and are in conformity with the observations of Fritz Ephraim (*loc. cit.*). The formation of pyro-arsenite is, however, not evidenced as mentioned in the earlier literature.

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